

EXPLORING THE NEED FOR ERGONOMIC INTERVENTIONS TO ALLEVIATE MUSCULOSKELETAL DISORDERS (MSD) AMONG CONSTRUCTION WORKERS AT QM BUILDERS

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ABSTRACT

The construction industry is a high-risk sector characterized by physically demanding tasks that contribute to the prevalence of lower back pain (LBP) and musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs). At QM Builders in Dumanjug, Cebu, Philippines inconsistent safety enforcement further exposed 60% of their construction workers to these risks, with LBP as the most prevalent condition. In this paper, an experimental design was used involving pre-test and post-test phases with 12 purposively selected construction workers reporting lower back pain. Tools such as the Modified Standard Nordic Questionnaire (MNSQ) and the Modified Brief Pain Inventory (BPI) were utilized to assess pain intensity and its interference with daily tasks. The initial prototype (Design 1) provided lightweight support but demonstrated limitations, including poor fit, weak straps, and slippage during heavy tasks. Based on user feedback, Design 2 was enhanced with an adjustable waist belt and a more flexible waistband, resulting in improved fit, stability, and overall user satisfaction. In particular, data on pain levels and comfort were collected before and after the ergonomic intervention, with most respondents aged 18–33 (58.33%) and having 4–6 years of experience (50%). Results showed no significant differences in lower back pain based on age or experience ($p > 0.05$). Prior to the intervention, 67% of workers reported severe pain and 33% moderate pain. After two weeks of back brace use, 92% reported mild or no pain, with no cases of severe pain. A paired t-test confirmed a significant reduction in pain levels, with mean scores decreasing from 4.89 to 1.07 ($t = 13.57, p = 3.25 \times 10^{-8}$), demonstrating the effectiveness of the ergonomic intervention. The study concluded that the ergonomic back brace proved to be a beneficial intervention for construction workers, demonstrating a consistent positive impact on lower back pain regardless of demographic differences.

Keywords: Ergonomic Back Brace, Lower Back Pain, Construction Industry, Modified Standard Nordic Questionnaire (MNSQ), Modified Brief Pain Inventory (BPI)

INTRODUCTION

In the construction industry, construction workers' work is physically demanding and a hazardous sector worldwide. It involves heavy lifting, repetitive tasks, bending, twisting, and prolonged standing and working in awkward positions (Lop et al., 2019). The activities that the workers perform often lead to musculoskeletal disorders MSDs that greatly affect the lower back pain, which is the most common health issue among construction workers. According to Lu (2022), many workers in the Philippines, particularly in the construction sector, lack adequate social protection. This increases their exposure to occupational hazards and hinders effective risk management. Lower Back Pain (LBP) is the leading cause of loss of health function worldwide (Wang et al., 2023). In terms of Despite the extensive prevalence of MSDs in the construction industry, effective ergonomic interventions remain limited. While tools such as exoskeletons and back braces show promise in mitigating risks (Bennett et al., 2023), the construction sector's slow adoption of new technologies, materials, and tools hinders their implementation (Setaki & Van Timmeren, 2022).

Globally, the construction industry represents that it is one of the largest labor sectors that was exposed to biomechanical hazards. The study of epidemiological studies consistently reports that construction workers experience a higher rate of musculoskeletal disorders compared to workers in the manufacturing and services industries. The lower back pain, in particular, has been associated with cumulative spinal loading, the repetitive posture and improper manual handling techniques. The chronic nature of the lower back pain not just only affects physical health but also it can lead to reduced the workers capacity , it can increased absenteeism and the long term disability risk. In developing economies, where the occupational safety regulations may be less strict and the burden becomes even more significant.

Developing countries like the Philippines, small and mediums sized construction firms often operates with limited occupational health monitoring systems. The workers typically just rely on physical endurance and experience rather than ergonomic intervention devices. The absence of structured ergonomic intervention results is increased the vulnerability to long-term injuries. The economic pressure may discourage the workers from reporting their pain symptoms as it can create absenteeism that can lead to income loss as it is important to their living . This socio-economic context intensifies the burden of lower back pain among Filipino construction workers.

At QM Builders in Dumanjug, Cebu, a prominent construction company with 17 years of industry experience, a preliminary survey using the Modified Standard Nordic Questionnaire found that 60% of workers experienced lower back pain while working. This study is based on both Ergonomic Theory and OHS Theory, highlighting the role of well-designed tools, equipment, and workplaces in supporting workers' health and performance, and in OHS Theory by emphasizing the importance of proactive hazard identification and risk reduction to ensure workplace safety. Combining these two theories, the study aims to explore how ergonomic interventions, such as back braces, help construction workers perform their tasks comfortably while reducing the risks of long-term injuries. It explains how the workplace design, work posture, and safety conditions contribute to the prevalence of lower back pain among construction workers. These theories support the implementation of ergonomic interventions to improve the working conditions of construction workers.

This study aims to explore the need for ergonomic interventions, specifically the design of an ergonomic back brace, to aid lower back pain and reduce the risk of MSDs experienced among construction workers. This research aims to answer the following questions: the demographics of construction workers in terms of age and years of experience in the construction industry, to what extent construction workers experience lower back pain before and after the intervention of an ergonomic back brace, and what ergonomic intervention can be developed to alleviate the musculoskeletal disorders among construction workers. The pain that construction workers experience not only affects the workers' health but also reduces their productivity and the safety in the job environment. This study was conducted to see if there are effective results of an ergonomic intervention back brace, which could reduce the workers' pain and help them perform their tasks comfortably.

The significance of this study is that the findings of this research will be beneficial to construction workers, QM Builders Management, Occupational Health and Safety Officers, and future researchers, as it is useful. This study addresses the daily challenges faced by construction workers, particularly their vulnerability to musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) such as lower back pain during their work. The focus of the thesis is to lower the risks of MSDs in QM Builders through the implementation of back braces as part of an ergonomic intervention strategy. Proven effective, the use of back braces could have broader applications within the construction industry.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

The study uses both experimental and collaborative research designs, which involved 12 construction workers who were experiencing lower back pain. It was conducted at QM Builders in Dumanjug, Cebu, Philippines. The twelve construction workers engaged in physically demanding tasks

were selected using purposive sampling. Participants were directly involved in lifting, carrying materials, bending, and repetitive manual labor. Two standardized tools were employed: the Modified Standard Nordic Questionnaire (MNSQ), which assesses the prevalence of musculoskeletal discomfort, and the Modified Brief Pain Inventory (BPI), which measures pain intensity before and after the intervention.

Figure 1. *Front and Back View Prototype Sketch of Design 1*

The figure illustrates the initial version of the ergonomic back brace. This design was part of a collaborative process that incorporated feedback from 12 construction workers and site supervisors at QM Builders to ensure functionality and comfort without restricting movement during physically demanding tasks

It was conducted in four phases: Pretest Phase that the participants completed the MNSQ and BPI to establish baseline pain levels; the Intervention Phase, in which a prototype ergonomic back brace was introduced and used during regular work tasks for approximately two weeks; Posttest Phase, in which the BPI was re-administered to assess changes in pain levels and Data Analysis, which used statistical analysis included descriptive statistics, paired t-test, and ANOVA to determine significance levels. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics that summarize the prevalence and mean pain scores. A paired sample t-test was conducted in order to determine whether differences between pretest and posttest pain levels were statistically significant. The one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to assess whether the years of work experience influenced pain reduction in terms of outcomes. A significance level of 0.05 was adopted. Additionally, the cost-benefit analysis was performed in order to evaluate the economic feasibility of implementing the ergonomic intervention back braces, which includes the estimation of projected benefits over five years and computation of the Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) and Net Present Value (NPV). The economic projections included that the estimated reductions in productivity loss, decreased

absenteeism, and minimized medical consultations related to musculoskeletal pain among construction workers. Standard discounting techniques were applied to determine long-term investment viability. This comprehensive methodological approach ensured that both clinical effectiveness and financial sustainability were systematically evaluated.

RESULTS

In this section, it demonstrated the analysis and interpretation of the data collected to answer the research questions posed in the statement of the problem. The findings are organized according to the sequence of the study's objectives and are discussed in relation to the literature reviewed. The results focus on evaluating the effectiveness of ergonomic interventions, such as a back brace, in reducing musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) among construction workers, based on data gathered through surveys and assessments.

Table 1

Demographic Profile of Construction Workers in terms of Age

AGE GROUP	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
18–33	7	58.33
34–49	2	16.67
≥ 50	3	25
TOTAL	12	100

This table presents the age distribution of construction workers, showing the frequency and percentage of respondents in each age group. The majority of the respondents (58.33%) are between 18 and 33 years old, indicating that a large portion of the workforce is composed of young individuals. The 34–49 age group comprises 16.67% of the respondents, suggesting a smaller representation of middle-aged workers. Meanwhile, 25% of the respondents are aged 50 and above. This reflects a significant number of older workers who may have been in the construction industry for many years

Table 2

Demographic Profile of Construction Workers in terms of Years of Experience

EXPERIENCE GROUP (YEARS)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
0-3	3	25
4-6	6	50

7 and above	3	25
TOTAL	12	100

This table demonstrated the demographic distribution of construction worker participants (N = 12) based on professional experience. Half of the participants (n = 6) fall within the 4–6-year experience range. A quarter of the respondents (25%) have 0 to 3 years of experience, suggesting that they are relatively new to the field. Another 25% of the workers have 7 or more years of experience. Although this group is smaller, their long exposure to physically demanding tasks increases the likelihood of experiencing the long-term effects of manual labor, such as chronic back pain, joint strain, or other symptoms related to musculoskeletal disorders.

Table 3

ANOVA Analysis of Average Pain Across Age Groups (Pre-test Results)

SUMMARY				ANOVA		
GROUPS (AGE)	COUNT	AVERAGE PAIN	VARIANCE	F STAT	P-VALUE	F CRIT
18-33	7	4.72	0.94	0.39	0.69	4.26
34-49	2	4.92	1.67			
50 Above	3	5.28	0.19			

The table shows the ANOVA results for pain reduction across the age: 18-33 (n=7), 34-49 (n=2), and 50 + (n=3). The analysis percentage of pain reduction between the age groups, $F(2,9) = 0.045$, $p = .95$. The p-value is greater than the standard alpha level of .05; the null hypothesis is retained.

Table 4

ANOVA Analysis of Average Pain Across Years of Experience Groups (Pre-test Results)

SUMMARY				ANOVA		
GROUPS (Yrs. Of Experience)	COUNT	AVERAGE PAIN	VARIANCE	FSTAT	P VALUE	F CRIT
0-3	3	4.50	0.58	0.46	0.64	4.25
4-6	6	4.92	1.16			
7 Above	3	5.22	0.28			

This table represents the One-way ANOVA results for average pre-test pain levels across three professional experience groups: 0–3 years ($n = 3$), 4–6 years ($n = 6$), and 7+ years ($n = 3$). The analysis indicates no statistically significant difference in baseline pain levels between groups, $F(2, 9) = 0.46$, $p = 64$. Since the p -value is greater than .05, the null hypothesis is retained.

Table 5

ANOVA Analysis of Average Pain Reduction (%) Between Pre-Test and Post Test Across Age Groups

SUMMARY			ANOVA			
GROUPS (AGE)	COUNT	AVERAGE PAIN REDUCTION(%)	VARIANCE	F STAT	P VALUE	F CRIT
18-33	7	76.80	57.05			
34-49	2	76.78	72.60			
50 Above	3	78.5	120.68	0.04483	0.95	4.25649

This table shows the ANOVA results for pain reduction across three age groups: 18–33 ($n = 7$), 34–49 ($n = 2$), and 50+ ($n = 3$). The analysis indicates no significant difference in the percentage of pain reduction between the age groups, $F(2, 9) = 0.045$, $p = .95$. Because the p -value is greater than the standard alpha level of .05, the null hypothesis is retained.

Table 6

ANOVA Analysis of Average Pain Reduction (%) Between Pre-Test and Post Test Across Years of Experience Groups

SUMMARY			ANOVA			
GROUPS(Yrs.of Experience)	COUNT	AVERAGE	VARIANCE	F STAT	P- VALUE	F CRIT
0-3	3	74.36	84.91			
4-6	6	76.95	65.24	0.45	0.65	4.25
7 ABOVE	3	80.62	53.55			

The table shows the one-way anovane-way ANOVA results for average pain reduction percentage across three groups of professional experience: 0–3 years ($n = 3$), 4–6 years ($n = 6$), and 7+ years ($n = 3$). The analysis indicates that years of experience did not have a statistically significant effect on pain reduction, $F(2, 9) = 0.45$, $p = .65$. Because the p -value is greater than the alpha level of .05, the null hypothesis is retained

Figure 2

Comparison of Lower Back Pain Levels Among Construction Workers Before and After Back Brace Intervention

This figure contains the distribution of the pain levels among construction workers before and after the intervention was implemented. After the use of the brace, a remarkable shift in pain levels can be observed. In the pre-test, the no pain 6.25 % for the pre-test, mild for 12.5 %, moderate is 37.5 %, and severe is 43.75 % while on the post -test side no pain is 18.75 %, mild was 31.25 %, the moderate is 37.5% and severe is 12.5% as the figure above illustrates.

Figure 3. *Front and Back View of the Final Ergonomic Back Brace Design 2*

The figure is the picture of the real-life front view and back view prototype design 2 as the final ergonomic intervention back brace among 12 construction workers. The final prototype was being utilized during the two-week intervention phase. This version incorporated finalized adjustable straps and lumbar reinforcement based on the initial collaborative feedback.

Figure 4. *Sketch by Parts of the Design 2*

The sketch by parts shows the individual components of the design separated from each other to clearly present each part and its function. It includes the waist belt assembly, rigid back support, elastic shoulder straps, fastening assembly, hot and cold compartment, reflective vest component, and breathable material layer. This view helps in understanding how each part is constructed and how they will be assembled step by step.

Figure 5. *The Whole Sketch of Ergonomic Back Brace Design 2*

The whole sketch with parts presents the complete assembled design, showing how all components are combined into one functional product. Each labeled part is positioned according to its actual placement, demonstrating the overall structure, support system, and functionality. This view provides a clear visualization of the final product and how the parts work together to ensure comfort, safety, and usability.

Table 7

Paired T-Test Results for Lower Back Pain Before and After Ergonomic Intervention

Respondents	Experimental n=12				
	PreTest	Post Test	Pain Reduction(%)	T Stat	P-value
R1	4.83	1.33	72.46		
R2	4.67	1	78.59		
R3	4	1.17	70.75		
R4	5.83	1	82.99	13.57	3.2523E-8
R5	6.5	1.17	82		
R6	5.17	1	80.83		
R7	3.83	1	73.98		
R8	5.33	1.5	71.86		
R9	5	0.67	86.6		
R10	3.67	1.33	63.93		

R11	4.17	1.17	71.94
R12	5.67	0.5	91.17

$\alpha = 0.05$

critical t value = 2.20

The distribution of lower back pain levels among construction workers (N = 12) before and after a back brace intervention. Data represent the percentage of participants reporting no pain, mild, moderate, or severe pain. There is a visible reduction in the "severe" category from 43.75% pre-test to 12.5% post-test, while the "no pain" and "mild" categories showed an increase following the intervention. This means the difference in scores is large enough to be considered meaningful and not just due to chance. The p-value was 3.2523×10^{-8} , which is much smaller than 0.05. This tells us the results are statistically significant, and we can be confident that using the back brace helped reduce pain.

Table 8

Hypothesis Testing Results on the Relationship Between Demographics, Back Pain Levels, and the Effect of the Ergonomic Back Brace

Hypothesis	Statistical Test Used	Test Statistic	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
H0: There is no significant relationship between the workers' demographics in terms of age and years of experience, and their baseline lower back pain levels.	One-way ANOVA (Age)	F= 0.39	0.69	Accept H0	Age group does not affect baseline pain.
	One-way ANOVA (Experience)	F= 0.46	0.64	Accept H0	Experience does not affect baseline pain.

H2: The lower back pain experienced by construction workers before the intervention of the ergonomic back brace is not significantly different from the pain experienced after the intervention.

3.2523E-8 Reject H_1 Back brace significantly reduced pain ($p < 0.05$).

Paired t-test $t = 13.57$

The table demonstrated the analysis of demographic factors revealed no significant associations between baseline pain levels and either age ($F = 0.39$, $p = 0.69$) or years of experience ($F = 0.46$, $p = 0.64$) through one-way ANOVA testing. The pain reductions in lower back pain following the ergonomic back brace intervention, as indicated by the paired t-test ($t = 13.57$, $p < 3.2523E-8$). The results revealed no significant differences in MSD-related pain across age or years of experience ($p > 0.05$). This is likely due to the small sample size ($n = 20$, analyzed $n = 12$) and uneven group distributions.

Table 9

Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) of the Ergonomic Back Brace Project

Projected Period	PV of the Benefits (PHP)	Total Cost (PHP)	BCR
1 Year	18,928.57	11,511.00	1.64
5 Years	86,055.78	11,511.00	7.48

The table demonstrated the calculated Benefit-Cost Ratio (BCR) for the ergonomic back brace project. The positive Net Present Values (NPV) in both the 1-year (PHP 7,417.57) and 5-year (PHP 74,544.78) projections indicate that the benefits significantly outweigh the costs. Likewise, the Benefit-Cost Ratios (BCR) of PHP 1.64 for the first year and PHP 7.48 for five years show an economically viable and beneficial project that offers a substantial return on investment.

DISCUSSION

The findings confirm that lower back pain is a significant occupational issue in the construction industry. The substantial and statistically significant reduction in pain levels following the ergonomic intervention supports the principles of Ergonomic Theory, that emphasizes the importance of aligning workplace tools with human biomechanical capacity to reduce strain. The absence of significant differences

across experience levels suggests that ergonomic support benefits workers universally, regardless of tenure. This shows the broad applicability of preventive ergonomic strategies in construction settings. Significant reduction in pain levels following the two-week consistent use of the ergonomic back brace demonstrates the effectiveness of the intervention. The statistically significant paired t-test result indicates that the observed improvement was not due to chance. These findings support the application of ergonomic principles in reducing physical strain and improving the workers' comfort during their physically demanding work. In an operational perspective, in terms of Cost-Benefit Analysis, a strong Benefit–Cost Ratio underscores the strategic value of proactive ergonomic investment rather than managing injuries reactively that integrates ergonomic devices into occupational safety programs that offers a measureable health and financial advantages.

Although the study provided meaningful findings, it is limited in terms of sample size and reliance on self-reported measures. Future researchers may consider larger sample size and a longer intervention period to further develop and validate the results. Despite the limitation, the results provide strong preliminary evidence that the ergonomic intervention back brace is an effective and economically sustainable intervention for reducing lower back pain in construction environment.

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